

The Information Technology and Its Role in Internal Monitoring

Kifaa Abdulkareem Shakir

University of Iraq - College of Engineering

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 30 September 2025</p>	<p>The quick, consecutive developments in the world of information technology have led to the use of computers in the systems of accountings and management of institutions in general. Thus, the modern approach of the internal monitoring systems was concentrated on the integrity between the general structure of internal monitoring and the other managements of the institution, which contributes in managing the institution in inappropriate circumstances (uncertainty) so that the institution is able to protect its existence and durability in the competition context with the rest of the institutions, through depending on the ability of the internal monitoring systems to develop the factors of efficiency and ensure the implementation of the plans constructed by the management. Therefore, the internal monitoring was depended on in reducing the percentage of risk the institution might be under, through determining the goals of the institution first, and then the expectations of possibility of the institution's goals being under different threats, and according to that the procedures of the internal monitoring are determined to reduce the risks, which provides some plausible guarantees in achieving the goals of the institution through providing developed and appropriate monitoring systems. Many challenges have arose as a result of competition between economical institutions on one hand, and the continuous development in the methods of the internal monitoring on the other, which led to the emergence of vast challenges in innovating and applying a modern technique of the internal monitoring system depending on the structure of the internal monitoring system and its ability to take in this new technique on computers, and the ability of its systems in providing the data and information to support the system's ability to adopt it. According to what was mentioned earlier, we will look into the subject of the research in five chapters, where the first chapter shows the methodology of the research, and the second chapter looks into the frame of the internal monitoring concepts, as for the third chapter, it takes the frame of information technology, concepts, while the fourth chapter was designated to study the effects of the role of information technology on the internal monitoring system, as for the fifth chapter, it is the epilogue of the research and the most important conclusions and recommendations that this research has reached.</p>
<p>Corresponding Author: Kifaa Abdulkareem Shakir</p>	
<p>KEYWORDS: Use of computers – Managements – Data – Competition – Continuous development – Challenges.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

Information technology has become one of the primary means of processing corporate data. Its ability to perform complex calculations has strengthened internal controls by providing new, innovative formulas for managing transactions quickly and efficiently. As a result, accounting and operational errors have significantly decreased, and reliance on the human element has decreased as well, allowing for increased accuracy and data quality. Information technology has fundamentally changed the methods and methodology of internal control systems in organizations by creating programs that are easy to use and install and can adapt to organizational

work. This has led to their widespread adoption. In turn, organizations have become more keen to rely on IT to keep pace with professional and scientific developments by establishing efficient and effective internal control systems. These systems ensure the implementation of organizational plans and administrative policies, protect assets, and guarantee the accuracy of financial and accounting data submitted to senior management. This allows management to make timely decisions. Many organizations have established independent departments for internal control systems to effectively and significantly achieve their goals.

Research Problem:

The research problem lies in determining the extent to which information technology can be leveraged to support internal control systems, given the lack of an internal control system in institutions. In light of the rise of information technology, the role of technology has grown in other activities. Other business sectors have witnessed development and advancement in the quality of services they provide, thanks to their use of information technology, which has created new applications characterized by high speed and efficiency in their work. However, internal control remains manual, with no mechanism to help it control and enhance employee efficiency. Meanwhile, the role of information technology has significantly and noticeably increased in other business sectors.

Importance of the Research:

The importance of the research stems from the significant role of internal audit in government institutions, given its effective role in achieving these institutions' objectives by creating a mechanism that regulates work. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of information technology as a technology that assists internal audit in processing data, enabling management to prepare and present reports more accurately and quickly than previously using outdated manual systems. Its importance also stems from its responsiveness to ongoing developments in information technology and its role in automated data processing.

Research objectives:

The research aims to highlight the role of information technology in enhancing the efficiency of internal control in light of the use of computers in government institutions. Its use helps address the scale of expansion in government institutions' operations by obtaining reliable accounting data to ensure the implementation of previously established administrative policies and organizational plans, while maintaining the objectives and not altering them.

Research Hypothesis:

The research hypothesis is based on several factors:

1. Information technology is considered an important method and tool for improving the efficiency and effectiveness of institutional performance in a sound and accurate manner.
2. Information technology plays a role in improving and developing the effectiveness of internal control.
3. The use of information technology reduces complex routine procedures when evaluating institutional performance.

Research Methodology:

The descriptive approach was followed, referencing sources and information found in books, university theses, and official documents related to this topic to demonstrate the importance of using information technology to achieve accurate and comprehensive control procedures.

Research Plan:

The research plan confirmed its importance through its five chapters. The first chapter reviewed the research methodology, the second chapter addressed the framework of internal control concepts, the third chapter addressed the framework of information technology concepts, and the fourth chapter examined the impact of the role of information technology on the internal control system. The fifth chapter presented the most important conclusions and recommendations reached by the research.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1- The Concept and Definition of Internal Control:

Definitions of internal control have varied with the different stages of its development. We will address some of these definitions:

It has been defined as (the standards, coordination methods, and organizational chart used within an organization, which aim to protect assets and review and control financial and accounting data to ensure their integrity and accuracy, enabling them to be relied upon to increase production efficiency and motivate employees to adhere to previously established administrative policies). (Al-Jubouri, 1991: 4)

It has also been defined by International Standard No. (400) of the International Federation of Accountants as (all procedures and policies implemented by organizations to help them achieve their objectives to the greatest extent possible, while ensuring high operational efficiency and consistent management, while adhering to a policy of protecting the organization's assets by detecting errors and preventing fraud, preparing documented financial and accounting information, and completing its records in a timely manner). (Bilal, 2014-2015: 5)

It is also defined as "the means that ensures the achievement of business objectives, ensuring that they do not fall short of what is planned." (Al-Jaafari, no year of publication: 402)

It is also defined as "the planning and organization of the project by management, and the associated means and measures used by the project to protect its assets, while testing the accuracy of financial and accounting data and the extent to which management relies on such data to develop production efficiency, in addition to encouraging the implementation of management policies as planned." (Qallala, 2013-2014: 65)

From these definitions, we can conclude a comprehensive definition of internal control, which is "the procedures and methods undertaken by management to implement planned administrative policies, as well as internal control, i.e., reviewing all data related to the organization's assets and ensuring the accuracy of the data provided to it for reliance, ensuring the success of the organization's work process and achieving high profits at the lowest possible cost."

Reasons for the Expansion of the Role of Internal Control:

It is well known that internal control system staff operate within the confines of the institution itself. Therefore, they certainly seek to serve the institution's management through the control process. This reflects internal control's interest in achieving everything that can lead to the institution's success and continuity. We can therefore conclude that this interconnectedness is one of the factors that has contributed to the expansion of internal control. These factors are as follows: (Juma, 2000: 94).

- The growth of institutions and expansion of their operations has made it necessary to rely on internal control systems, such as budgets, division of labor, and analytical statements, to a greater extent than before.
- Institutional owners and auditors recognize the importance of internal control systems and work to improve and strengthen them, making them more reliable for accounting work.
- a quality internal control system helps management protect its assets from potential risks or errors by providing comprehensive protection and preserving assets.
- it provides management with accurate, reliable, and periodic data on which to base all its decisions through the presence of a successful and effective internal control system.
- It provides government agencies with accurate data on various types of establishments in the country, assisting them in formulating economic plans and exercising government oversight.
- Delegating powers and responsibilities to sub-departments within government institutions is necessary.
- The development of institutional procedures in administrative and accounting systems has fundamentally changed the internal control system.

2- Objectives of the Internal Control System:

Institutions establish internal control systems to achieve their objectives, preserve their assets, ensure the smooth running of operations, and comply with senior management's instructions and policies. Therefore, management seeks to establish efficient and effective internal control systems that protect the institution from potential problems. The responsibility for implementation lies in ensuring that internal control systems carry out the organizational plans established by management, including the associated procedures and methods. These are as follows: (Abu Hajar, 2021: 10).

- Authority within the institution: This is achieved through precise and strict implementation of all laws, procedures, and instructions contained in work systems and regulations.
- Protection of the institution's assets: This refers to the protection of the institution's actual assets and records. This protection is divided into two parts. The first part is accounting protection related to recording asset movements. The second part is physical protection from tampering, theft, damage, and other such matters.

- Ensuring the quality and accuracy of information: This goal is the most important because the organization relies on this information to make decisions and develop future plans.
- Improving performance: It refers to the organization's ability to achieve its pre-defined goals with the lowest possible cost while maintaining quality and excellence.

3- Components of the Internal Control System:

The internal control system is built on a set of key components that management follows to achieve its objectives. These components fall under two categories: accounting and administrative. The administrative components must be present in the internal control system, as follows: (Al-Jabri, 2013-2014: 32).

The first branch is the accounting components of internal control. This branch includes processes and procedures in accounting records that prepare and analyze information to verify its accuracy and integrity. This is the core and foundation of accounting control.

- Accounting Manual: The process of classifying financial accounts in accordance with the organization's accounting system to ensure achievement of its objectives.
 - Accounting documents: This documentary cycle is considered a primary source of accounting entries and evidence with a high degree of efficiency to help the organization achieve a sound control system.
 - Accounting Books: These are a set of books, such as the general journal and related auxiliary journals, which are tailored to the nature of the organization's work and activity.
 - Electronic Devices: Computers are one of the automated tools used within the accounting system to complete and control the organization's work through various information programs.
 - Asset inventory: A physical inventory of an organization's assets that compares the assets recorded in accounting records with their actual physical existence, whether they are current or fixed assets.
 - Planning budget: This is an internal control role that identifies the reasons for deviations between planned objectives and actual results. This comparison helps identify the root causes of problems and attempts to avoid them by defining authority and responsibility, as well as setting precise operational standards when defining the organization's objectives and functions accurately.
- Section Two: Administrative Components of Internal Control The characteristics that the organization's administrative structure must possess to achieve its stated objectives are as follows:
- Organizational Structure Appropriateness: This involves creating an organizational structure that is efficient and compatible with the nature of the organization's work and objectives. It is characterized by simplicity and clarity.

“The Information Technology and Its Role in Internal Monitoring”

- Human Resources: Select competent employees, especially those in personnel departments, who have the experience and competence to implement the interconnectedness and coordination between the organization's objectives and its administrative and accounting organization.
- Integrity of Duties: Performance levels and standards significantly impact job integrity in each department within the organization. These levels and standards significantly impact the effectiveness of internal control and the efficiency of business results. They ensure good performance through accurate decision-making based on the competence of the human element. This is achieved by ensuring the availability of standards for measuring employee performance. All of this contributes to correcting any deviations by comparing planned results with actual results and taking the necessary measures in response.
- Asset protection: Providing complete protection for the organization's assets requires establishing procedures and policies that prevent leakage or embezzlement of those assets. Another protection measure is providing accurate accounting and financial data and reports to support the internal control system administratively.
- Internal Audit: Creating an administrative department within the organization called "Internal Audit" helps the internal control system perform its work properly, providing support and assistance.
- Information and Communications: This refers to the financial reporting information system and the accounting information system, as well as the organization's processes for recording and processing information related to the financial statements and communicating it to the intended user. This is accomplished through the accounts specified in the financial statements related to the processing of transactions, supporting data, documents, and accounting records. This is achieved through the proper functioning of accounting processes and activities used to prepare and process the financial statements correctly.
- Monitoring: (Al-Khatib, 2010: 13) These are the procedures followed to implement various control aspects to ensure they are operating according to the established objectives. This is intended to achieve the effectiveness and efficiency of the internal control system. The various components of internal control must be continuously evaluated and maintained by management to determine the controls in place while simultaneously ensuring they are successful in achieving the purpose for which they were established. This allows for modifications, if necessary, based on sources that may be external, such as customer objections to these controls. This leads to an assessment of the quality of internal control performance and the effectiveness of its role.

5. Components of the Internal Control System: (Yahya et al., 1996: 48)

- Control Environment: The internal control environment is the foundation that influences the approach and direction taken by senior management regarding the importance of internal control. The control environment connects all other components of the internal control system. Therefore, senior management's policy determines the philosophy and working method of internal control, given its relevance and connection to it.
- Risk Assessment: These are the control activities that assist the accounting system and internal control system in ensuring accurate information is available to address risks related to achieving the organization's objectives. They also determine the mechanism for dealing with these risks and how to reduce them to an acceptable level, whether internal or external. These risks may be financial risks, such as liquidity risks, credit risks, etc., or administrative risks, such as theft, forgery, embezzlement, etc.
- Monitoring Activities: This refers to the extent to which the control employee is aware of the activities and policies used by the organization to monitor the control activities related to financial reporting, and how these activities and policies are used to implement corrective actions, monitor deviations from the plan, and determine responsibility for them.

6- Characteristics of the Internal Control System: (Salem, 2005: 253-254)

To achieve the desired benefit of an internal control system, it must possess the following characteristics:

- Effectiveness: This refers to the use of a good and advanced control system that prevents errors and detects deviations before they occur, whenever possible, and then addresses them in a manner that ensures they do not occur in the future. The causes are identified and corrected as quickly as possible in order to achieve the organization's goals.
- Suitability: This refers to the suitability of the organization's control system to the nature of its activity and size. When the organization is small, a simple, uncomplicated control system is preferred, unlike large and massive organizations, which require the use of more robust control tools that are commensurate with the organization's size and scope of activity.
- Accuracy: In order to accurately reflect the financial position of an organization at the end of the financial period, the control system must be able to access accurate, correct, and timely data on the organization's performance. This data must be verified and verified from information sources, including accounting records and documents, and must be continuously monitored to detect errors in a timely manner, allowing for prompt and proper correction.
- Cost-saving control system: The primary objective of its existence is to reduce losses and wasted expenditures. If

a highly advanced control system is available and used in control systems, it can be controlled using simpler systems with lower costs. Therefore, the organization will not need a system whose costs exceed the benefits of its use, as the benefits of its use do not outweigh its costs.

- **Integration:** The control system must accommodate all organizational plan standards, in addition to integrating the plans developed with the approved control systems.
- **Timeliness:** Delayed information loses its usefulness, no matter how important. Therefore, it is essential to establish a good control system that receives information in a timely manner, especially from those responsible for preparing reports and data upon which plans and decisions are based.
- **Flexibility:** Adapting to emerging organizational variables, which underpins the success of the control system, as the similarity of deviations and problems requires an appropriate approach to address them. Flexibility means the ability to modify and innovate to suit changing circumstances and events.
- **Clarity:** The clarity of the control system in its policies and procedures reflects the clarity and purpose of the system, supporting the use of relied-upon standards and indicators when comparing actual results with planned ones, facilitating the process of reporting a defect or deviation when discovered.

7. The concept of information technology:

The world is witnessing successive developments and an increasing transformation in the field of communication devices and means, computers and their software, and the huge amount of information that is growing and moving easily and smoothly between the countries of the world, making the matter of information technology an important and inevitable means required by institutions of different sizes and types in order to keep pace with technical progress in a huge competitive environment as a result of the world entering an advanced era within the limits of information technology as a competitive advantage that all institutions seek, regardless of their activities.

We have discussed some definitions of information technology. We will mention a few of them.

Information technology is "the tools and technologies used by organizations that are characterized by self-interaction when carrying out computer-based activities. These tools assist management in collecting, storing, transferring, processing, and retrieving data" (Yassin, 2009: 44). (Yassin, 2009, p. 44).

It is also defined as "the use of modern technologies to improve the efficiency of products and systems that process, generate, and manage information, thereby providing organizations with a competitive advantage in making sound decisions using computer and communications technology" (Al-Hasban, 2009: 16).

It is also defined as "databases, networks, equipment, programs, etc., that focus on using information to improve work performance" (Kawja, 2012–2013: 21).

Another definition is "computer-related technologies used to present and process information through the tools and methods required by the user" (Miami et al., 2014: 831).

A final definition is "programs consisting of computer hardware, software, and other communication tools managed by experienced individuals to enhance institutional performance" (Jabouri, 2009: 141).

Based on these definitions, we can arrive at a comprehensive definition of information technology: "The use of computers and other advanced tools and methods to process databases, achieving speed and accuracy by storing, processing, transforming, and retrieving them to produce reliable information for making appropriate decisions at the appropriate time."

8. The Importance of Information Technology for the Internal Control System

Information technology and the qualitative changes it has brought to technical and scientific knowledge are major catalysts for business activities within organizations. Due to its capabilities and potential, information technology is a fundamental technical tool for all business fields. IT's ability to perform extremely fast, large-scale digital calculations and provide organizations with accurate, rapid, and low-cost communications is evident. IT also stores vast amounts of data and information while preserving its integrity. This allows all users, from all over the world, to access this information quickly and easily. This increases the effectiveness and efficiency of those responsible for it, whether in one location or multiple locations. In conclusion, information technology is an advanced means controlled by a sensitive and precise electronic system that reduces human effort. Nevertheless, information technology remains a tool that people can use to achieve the desired processes and outputs. (Farida et al., 2013-2014: 21).

Information Technology Trends in Internal Control Systems:

The shift in technology used to process, publish, and compile financial information and data through the use of information technology has led to clear changes to traditional tools used in dealing with information and data. This has helped enhance the capacity and efficiency of the control system in its financial processing, which is characterized by suitability, speed, detail, and objectivity compared to previous manual and traditional processes (Bolton et al., 1998, 53).

Information technology has provided tremendous potential to enhance the performance of the internal control system, including personnel, tools, and structures. Its advantages include its versatility and diversification, in addition to its relatively low cost. This has made the internal control system more responsive, capable, and flexible in adapting to changes in the corporate environment. Thus, we

can summarize the most important information technology trends in internal control systems:

- It is considered an effective tool for reorganizing and reducing expenses and reducing the human cadre, especially in middle management, all of which serves the interests and benefits of organizations.
- Its use leads to expanded oversight by senior management, which leads to the delegation of decision-making to executive (middle) management. This trend is called centralized oversight and decentralized decision-making. It combines two approaches simultaneously (centralization and decentralization), achieving high responsiveness and flexibility in the results of the oversight system.
- It has helped create new communication methods through the communications network, both within and outside the organization, increasing the speed of information exchange, processing, flow, and development.
- It has contributed to enhancing the oversight system's ability to successfully adapt to the organization's work environment by processing, retrieving, and storing information, then presenting it to decision-makers in a timely manner. This has been reflected in the effectiveness and efficiency of internal oversight. (Al-Abdali, 2003: 45-46)
- Reducing the storage space for information and converting it to electronic files that can be retrieved directly from the database at any time, with the ability to update stored information whenever necessary.
- Facilitating the electronic exchange of data with other information systems to achieve integration between them.
- Facilitating the performance of various financial processes and operations, utilizing their ability to provide electronic tools such as statistical and mathematical methods (Hashem, 2006, pp. 80-81).

III. REFLECTION OF THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ON THE INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM

The electronic use of data and information has affected the procedures and methods of internal control through the rapid developments that have occurred in the accounting and financial systems of institutions in general, which has led to fundamental changes in the approach and method of internal control compared to the traditional manual use of data and information.

1-What is Electronic Internal Control?

Electronic control has been defined in several ways, including the following:

- It is "the method of using electronic information resources after collecting data for an organization's activities in an integrated and comprehensive system that provides the advantage of centralized data,

leading to high-quality control with speed and reduced costs" (Lubke et al., 2005: 691).

- It has also been defined as "the use of advanced electronic means and methods to monitor an organization's activities and transactions, thus reducing time and effort and reducing costs, in order to achieve targeted results with minimal difficulty." (Juma, 2009: 289).
- It has also been defined as "procedures that oblige employees to adhere to the organization's laws by monitoring their work performance to identify violators electronically, while creating a work environment in which the employee feels they are under surveillance through monitoring devices that act as a deterrent to anyone who attempts to slow down at work." (Amin, 2009: 25).

In light of the aforementioned definitions, we can derive a definition. Comprehensive electronic control as (the process of observing and following up on the activities and performance of employees within the institution with the aim of detecting deviations as soon as possible using advanced technological means and devices to achieve the institution's goals of advancing to a work system characterised by a high competitive advantage among its market share).

2- Characteristics of Information Technology in Internal Control: (Al-Adly et al., 1986: 406)

Information technology has imposed a new reality on institutions, particularly on the internal control system. This reality requires keeping pace with these developments and the importance of changing old, traditional methods and replacing them with advanced methods to achieve goals and tasks with high efficiency and effectiveness within the limits of available resources, and then directing them in the best possible ways and means. Therefore, internal control systems focus on adopting controls derived from information technology. Therefore, possessing an understanding of information technology systems and their capabilities within control controls is a top priority for the organization's senior management, due to the increasing intensity and severity of competition, given the need for quick and effective decision-making to enable organizations to exist and continue while maintaining their market position. Therefore, it is important to identify the characteristics of information technology in meeting internal control needs, making it qualified to provide the necessary information required by senior management after converting raw data into useful and reliable information for use in making sound and rational decisions:

- Speed of calculations: This is the provision of information to decision-makers in a timely manner, characterized by the speed required to make quick and rational decisions that support the organization's competitive position in global markets. It also helps in using ratio and comparison analysis methods and extracting parameters and indicators that help control quickly evaluate performance.
- 2-Accuracy of Accounting Operations: This helps the

organization monitor its internal and external branches due to the quality and accuracy of the information the system provides to senior management.

- Consistency in Accounting Operations: Improving and modernizing internal control methods by leveraging the capabilities of computers provided for internal control of daily operations and the ability to perform audits of results through audit programs prepared and ready for this purpose.
- Reliability of Accounting Operations: This is the ability to perform a large and complex operation in a short time without operational or accounting errors, in addition to reducing reliance on human resources.
- Storage of Accounting Operations Data: This is the ability to store all information and data in electronic files that can be retrieved at any time. Control also helps in quickly retrieving information and data stored in computer memory, which helps control review certain matters.

3- Financial Transactions in the Light of Information Technology:

Information technology has played a significant role in the business environment. Its most important characteristic at the present time is the dynamism of information technology in all fields, due to its impact on various activities and transactions. It provides an effective and distinct internal control system, which constitutes a significant element in corporate management and a key pillar that helps achieve corporate objectives. It also creates systems that help ensure adherence to and compliance with legislation, laws, rules, procedures, policies, and plans, in addition to effective and sound internal control rules that reduce the problems and difficulties that may befall the organization. Therefore, establishing a sound system within the organization that communicates information to all levels of management is achieved through information technology, which helps create sound internal control and efficient oversight that addresses all deviations, leads to the financial soundness of the organization, preserves its integrity, and maintains it at a competitive level. Therefore, institutions are keen to utilize information technology in several aspects of their activities to develop the services they provide and achieve their goals through the use of information technology in the field of financial transactions and control when conducting the following operations: (Yahya et al., 1996: 48).

- Electronic Financial Documents: The type of documentary form is determined, including settlement, receipt, disbursement, and inventory entry and exit, to determine the type of data used for financial transactions. This is then recorded based on allocating one or more pages of the program according to the type of financial transaction. Data is also recorded in the journal and general ledger simultaneously.
- Electronic Books and Records: Financial transactions are recorded within electronic computers in the form of electronic files, instead of traditional books and records

in the form of columns, to record both debit and credit values.

- Electronic Reporting: Relying on computer outputs and considering them as reports and lists for the decision-making process, these reports are the foundation that helps departments solve their problems and detect deviations in a timely manner. These computers also feature centralized document storage after the information is entered, rather than being scattered across the organization's departments as in the past.
- Computer Output: This is a method for displaying previously entered results and information in the form of systematic reports.
- Computer Journal Recording: Combining the journal recording process with the ledger recording process into a single process, reducing the chance of errors while saving time and effort by merging certain financial transactions.
- Electronic Data Analysis: This involves arriving at realistic results based on the information and data inputs, providing a clear picture for decision-makers to take the necessary action.

3- The most important requirements of information technology on internal control:

To understand the impact of information technology on internal control, we must address the following factors:

- Philosophy of operating method: Electronic data processing revolves around the approach senior management takes in investing its funds.
- Institutional structure: The structure of the institution relies on a centralized or decentralized basis for electronic data processing, based on the policy followed by management in making its decisions.
- Methods of the administrative control system: These are the management's trends and ideas in its work environment when processing data based on changes in its policies and procedures, through the retention of programs and the feasibility of accessing computer documents and records.
- Management's policy toward its employees: This includes training and evaluating employees on electronic programs within computers.

Therefore, information technology has restructured the methods of extracting reports and processing their data. This has resulted in the emergence of some problems that must be addressed in order to find solutions when implementing them (Al-Hasban, 2008: 263).

Adapting Internal Control Methods to the Information Technology Environment:

Two main groups of control methods have been identified in the information technology environment: application control methods and general control methods. Therefore, the user must have knowledge of financial and accounting

matters to be able to develop a system that is difficult to penetrate.

First - Application Control Methods: The term "application control methods" refers to methods used in electronic information, performed by the electronic data processing department, to provide a reasonable degree of assurance regarding the accuracy of data recording and processing operations and the preparation of reports. Applied control methods fall into three types: (Amin, previous source).

1- Input Control: The objective of this control is to ensure the accuracy of data recorded on computers within programs designed for this purpose and received by the data processing department. This is achieved by reviewing document cycles, monitoring substantive and formal requirements, and monitoring data flow and compliance. This is done in accordance with internal regulations, systems, and procedures manuals, to ensure a reasonable degree of certainty for data processing department approval and the accuracy of its conversion to a degree that enables computers to recognize it, delete parts of it, make illegal modifications to the transmitted data, print a copy of it, or lose it. These methods include re-entering, rejecting, or correcting previous data. They also include the accuracy, comprehensiveness, and verification of data used in the information system, such that these methods include (tabulating and listing the documents from which information is taken, documenting and reviewing the entered data by the authorized person, and using serial numbers in data entry), followed by displaying and analyzing the data. Therefore, testing information inputs at an early stage has several reasons, the most important of which are: (Musa, 2008: 39).

- The ability to refer to the initial documents to determine the reason for the rejection and then correct the rejected data during the entry stage.

- Data prepared and processed by computer is not necessarily good data, but it simply means that it was entered correctly.

- It is always better to ensure that the data is safe and error-free after the initial stages of circulation and processing, as the correction process for data entries is not required to continue.

- The quality of the inputs will determine the quality of the outputs, meaning that good inputs will lead to good outputs, and vice versa. Therefore, attention must be paid to the inputs because they are the database for the outputs.

2- Data processing and control methods: This involves processing all authorized operations without neglecting any of them. This means providing a reasonable degree of assurance regarding the implementation of electronic data processing according to specific applications, due to the difficulty of modifying inputs except using a new program, with no possibility of manipulation. It is also necessary to ensure that the data stored within computers is correct. Therefore, the focus is on (the integrity of computer performance, the accuracy of modifications to computers, the

integrity of operating instructions from an accounting perspective, and the presence of self-control methods within the program). The role of data processing is to translate data into a format that produces a regularly readable image that helps decision-makers make decisions that are in the organization's best interest. Therefore, it is important that the data (inputs) be error-free to reach correct, error-free decisions. (Abdul Wahab et al., 2003: 124)

3- Output Control: This is a confirmation of the validity of data processing operations and the integrity of outputs, such as accounting statements or reports, and their circulation by authorized individuals. At this stage, procedures must be implemented that will highlight any errors after the completion of the operating process. This does not mean preventing errors, as is the case with the data entry stage. These procedures include:

- Establishing a specific template for the report format.
- Report content reflects the data stored in the files.
- Communicating reports to authorized individuals.
- Integrity of accounting operations and statements.
- Analysis of accounting statements and financial and accounting reports.

Therefore, the most important method of output control is the final output data and determining its effectiveness through a team member, i.e., knowledge of the information contained in the operational results. This is achieved by conducting some data tests on the output results, the most important of which are: (Abdul Wahab et al., 2003: 127).

A- Calculation Accuracy Testing: This involves performing simple calculations to test the validity and accuracy of the operational process. An example of this is that the net amounts, when the total deductions are added, will be equal to the total amounts.

B- Effectiveness Testing: If the final computer outputs show some inconsistent data for some operations, such as the appearance of numbers and amounts exceeding the maximum permissible wage rate or otherwise, or conversely, the appearance of numbers and amounts exceeding the minimum permissible rate, etc., then the error can be identified, recognized, and subsequently corrected.

C- Completeness and Comprehensiveness Test: This involves highlighting any deficiency or error in any of the required data processing. An example of this is the bank statement, which must ensure that all transactions that occurred during the month appear on both the debit and credit sides.

It is worth noting that there are several factors that must be taken into account when determining good control controls, represented by the operational objectives of control methods in their applications, namely: (Khadija, 2002: 74).

- The authority to approve transactions.
- The comprehensiveness and accuracy of data.
- Data entry, processing, and then outputs must be timely.
- Establishing protection systems for inputs, outputs, and computer operations files to maintain the confidentiality of information.

- Maintaining computer hardware and tools.

Second - General Control Methods: General control methods have a critical impact on data processing operations.

These methods include the following:

- Employee Control Methods: (Al-Sabban, 2003: 29). It may also be called organizational control methods, as the operation of a data processing system relies on individuals to configure the system itself, enter data, supervise the preparation of this data on computers, and present the outputs to specialists who have access to these reports. This is done using approved safeguards to ensure the proper and appropriate performance of these functions and processes.
- System File Protection: This involves establishing systems to protect information system tools and data, including magnetic files, discs, and tapes, from any negligence or neglect, whether intentional or unintentional.
- System Monitoring Team: The system monitoring team consists of one or more individuals responsible for using and establishing control methods over the application of control methods, encouraging their adoption, and addressing any malfunctions and shortcomings. The size of the team varies from one institution to another, depending on its size and the nature of its activity. The team may perform functions such as testing the safety of computer hardware and software operations, determining responsibilities, avoiding errors, and avoiding them as much as possible. (Al-Sawafiri et al., 2002: 367)
- Information System Review: This process is a control method in itself, as most control methods are useless unless implemented correctly and properly to prevent errors and prevent their continuation. Therefore, the auditor is responsible for the proper implementation of these procedures. The review aims to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the information system through control methods over accounting and financial applications. (Al-Sabban, previous source: 44-45).
- Computer Hardware Control Methods: Computers and their associated devices are considered one of the fixed assets owned by the institution and are expensive. Therefore, necessary preventive measures must be taken to protect them from vandalism and malfunction, with the possibility of material losses to these devices resulting from accidental, deliberate, or unintentional incidents. Therefore, security and protection measures for these devices are essential to ensure the management and sustainability of the control system, and to ensure the utilization of these devices by the institution's central units, such as data

processing, files, tape recorders, and information and data entry and extraction devices. (Al-Taie, 2004: 127)

4- Developing Information Technology Methods Used in Internal Auditing:

It is preferable to utilize technology in the field of auditing and update its methods using electronic tools. This is because old manual methods are no longer suitable for storing, retrieving, and analyzing information and data, which represent a vast amount of institutional work. Furthermore, statistical, engineering, and mathematical methods are not used in data analysis, as there is a pressing need for objectivity, integrity, and accuracy of the data and information used in the auditing process. To achieve these goals, a set of methods that contribute to the auditing process must be employed, as follows:

A. Adopting the statistical sampling method when evaluating and selecting samples.

B. Using advanced statistical methods when analyzing data that is difficult to analyze using traditional methods.

C. To ensure the accuracy of accounting treatments, the integrity of data and information, and the objectivity of the extracted information, a method of self-control and arbitration must be followed to complete the recording and processing processes.

D. To highlight anomalous numbers and symbols in data, it is preferable to update computer programs to provide greater clarity.

C. When preparing lists and reports of various types, it is preferable to use the graphical presentation and disclosure method.

H - To correct errors and make adjustments, a feedback method must be followed. (Jawad, 2010: 25).

5- Developing internal control systems using information technology:

Computers are an extension and deepening of the capabilities of software operators, as they are characterized by high accuracy and speed, and these qualities are their most important limitations. However, at the same time, they cannot determine an ultimate goal when preparing specific data, as the goal is determined by computer operators. To increase confidence in the programs used to process data, they must be configured to align with internal control systems to minimize problems resulting from new changes to these programs and systems. The development decision is made by a team authorized in electronic operations, as well as key users and internal auditors, whether the development requires purchasing new tools or programs or upgrading old ones. Humans prepare the data lists, and computers can only operate in the manner specified by the system. Furthermore, the operating staff in charge of inputs and outputs achieve success in the proper input process. As for departments that use databases and information to store information shared with computers and other functions, the data manager is

responsible for the operation of the databases and providing the necessary protection. The expansion of the scope of project work has led to the use of computers in financial and non-financial operations, as a result of the burdens placed on management in all activities and at all levels, and the expansion of the use of computers from commercial and industrial fields to other fields such as engineering, medicine, and others. (Al-Nawas, 2007: 33)

V. CONCLUSIONS

Internal control systems play a significant and important role in facilitating and assisting management in its tasks in terms of oversight and performance monitoring, achieving institutional objectives by measuring their success in preserving their assets. They have become an integral part of management through their role in ensuring the survival, continuity, and growth of institutions.

Advances in modern technologies, information and communications technology (ICT), have profoundly impacted not only the growth of institutions, but also their performance and the acceleration of technological progress. Therefore, they now strive to acquire the latest innovations through the use of modern technology, as this helps to enhance the efficiency, effectiveness, and development of the institution by improving its performance, maintaining its survival, and retaining its market share in the face of significant competition from other activities and businesses. In light of the above, the research reached a set of conclusions and recommendations, as follows:

First - Conclusions:

1. The effective use of information technology enhances the effectiveness of the internal control system by delivering accurate and timely information and results to all stakeholders in the business environment.

2- The use of information technology provides quality, speed, and accuracy in operational results, contributing to the development of a robust control system characterized by accuracy and speed.

3- The use of information technology is characterized by the detection and correction of errors in their early stages, which helps address deviations in a timely manner and find effective solutions.

4- The concept of internal control under traditional use is no different from that under the use of modern technology in terms of objectives and key elements, except for the difference in methods and approaches for implementing tasks.

5- The concept of internal control has evolved from its role in protecting corporate assets, confirming the accuracy of financial information, and detecting violations to a broader concept of increasing operational efficiency, in addition to adhering to the laws and policies of economic units.

6- The use of information technology helps organizations ensure their continued growth and maintaining their market share.

Second - Recommendations:

1- Full reliance on the use of information technology, given its potential for data speed and accuracy, regardless of its size, while gradually moving away from traditional methods.

2- Keeping pace with contemporary technological developments to enhance the efficiency of employees working in regulatory systems through continuous training and qualifications to enhance their skills in electronic work.

3- Protecting and safeguarding computers from damage, data theft, or theft of the devices themselves.

4- Keeping institutions abreast of modern technologies in regulatory work, which provides them with the opportunity to survive and develop.

5- Providing attention to the technical personnel responsible for implementing work, while developing instructions and procedures to regulate the work carried out.

6- Taking into account the variables and developments in the surrounding environment, which contributes to achieving the efficiency and effectiveness of information systems in a manner that serves the institution's objectives on an ongoing basis..

REFERENCES

1. Hashem Al-Jaafari - (Principles of Public Finance and Financial Legislation) - 3rd Edition.
2. Ahmed Helmy Juma (2000) - "The Modern Introduction to Computer Auditing" - 1st Edition - Dar Al-Safa for Publishing and Distribution - Amman, Jordan.
3. Khaled Ragheb Al-Khatib - (Financial and Internal Control in the Public and Private Sectors) - Arab Publishing and Distribution Library - 1st Edition - Amman, Jordan - 2010.
4. Fouad Al-Sheikh Salem - (Modern Administrative Concepts) - Jordanian Book Center - 2005.
5. Saad Ghaleb Yassin - (Fundamentals of Management Information Systems and Information Technology) - Dar Al-Manahj for Publishing and Distribution - (Amman, Jordan) - 2009.
6. Atallah Ahmed Suwailem Al-Hasban - (Auditing and Internal Control in the Accounting Information Systems Environment) - First Edition - Part One - Dar Al-Rayah - (Amman, Jordan) - 2009.
7. Lubke, Alvin Arens and James, translated by Dr. Muhammad Muhammad Abdul Qader Al-Daisy (Modern Auditing and Assurance - Review: An Integrated Approach) - 2005 - Dar Al-Marikh - Riyadh.
8. Ahmed Helmy Juma - (Modern Auditing and Assurance - Problems and Responsibilities, Tools and Services) - 2009 - Dar Safaa for Publishing and Distribution - Amman.
9. Al-Adly, Youssef Awad, Al-Azma, Muhammad Ahmad, and Al-Bassam, Sadiq Muhammad

- (Introduction to Financial Accounting), First Edition, Kuwait, Dhat Al-Salasil Publications, 1986.
10. Lutfi Amin, (An Applied Study in Auditing), University House for Publishing, Alexandria, Egypt, 2009.
 11. Nasr Ali Abdel-Wahab, Shehata Al-Sayed Shehata, and Adel Nemat Allah Naguib, (Studies in Advanced Auditing), University House for Publishing, Alexandria, Egypt, 2003.
 12. Muhammad Samir Al-Sabban - (Auditing Theory and Implementation Mechanisms) - University House for Publishing - Alexandria - Egypt 2003.
 13. Fathi Rizq Al-Sawafiri (Modern Trends in Internal Control and Auditing) - New University House for Publishing - Alexandria - Egypt 2002.
 14. 14- Muhammad Abd al-Husayn al-Faraj al-Ta'i - (Advanced Management Information Systems) - Wael Publishing and Distribution House - Amman - Jordan - 2004.
 15. Brabah Bilal (Evaluating the Role of Internal Auditors in Improving the Internal Control System in Economic Institutions) Master's Thesis - Management Sciences - University of M'hamed Bouguerra, Boumerdes (2014-2015).
 16. Asmaa Salman Zidan Al-Jabouri - (Control Programs in Light of Changes in the General Price Level - An Applied Study in the General Establishment for Leather Industries) Master's Thesis - University of Baghdad - 1991.
 17. Zakaria Qallala - (The Role of External Audit in Evaluating the Internal Control System) - Master's Degree in Finance and Accounting - Mohamed Khider University, Biskra (2013-2014).
 18. Sameh Refaat Abu Hajar - (The Role of Internal Audit as a Mechanism for Evaluating Internal Control Systems in Light of the Application of Corporate Governance) - Master's Degree - Faculty of Commerce, Cairo University - 2010.
 19. Mohamed Ali Mohamed Al-Jabri - (Evaluating the Role of the Internal Auditor in Improving the Internal Control System of Accounting Information Systems in Insurance Companies Operating in Yemen) - Master's Degree - Arab Academy for Banking and Financial Sciences, Sana'a, Yemen (2013-2014).
 20. Bashir Kawaja - (The Role of Information and Communication Technology in Improving Internal Communication in Public Hospital Institutions) - Master's Thesis - Specializing in Information Systems and Management Control - Faculty of Economics, Commerce, and Management Sciences - University of Ouargla - (2012-2013).
 21. Bouali Farida, Fawdil Hakima - (The Role of Information and Communication Technology in Improving Internal Communication in Institutions) - Master's Degree - Specialization in Financial and Banking Economics - College of Economics, Commerce and Management Sciences - Akli Mohand Ou El Hadj University - Bouira - (2013-2014).
 22. Ikhlas Hazza Karim Al-Abdeli - (Using Automated Methods in the Accounting Information System - Proposed Methods at Rafidain Bank - Nineveh) - Master's Thesis - College of Administration and Economics - University of Mosul - 2003.
 23. Yahya Ziad Hashim - (The Use of Information Technology in Economic Units and Its Impact on Accounting Information Systems - A Study of a Selected Sample of Iraqi Companies) - PhD Thesis - College of Administration and Economics - University of Mosul - 2006.
 24. Ramadan Khadija - (Developing Internal Control Systems to Detect Errors and Fraud in E-Commerce to Increase the Effectiveness of External Auditing) - Master's Thesis - Suez Canal University - Egypt - 2002.
 25. Rafid Abdul Nawas - (Obstacles Facing Accounting Employees in Performing Their Profession in a Computer-Used Environment and Ways to Overcome Them) - PhD Thesis, Arab Institute of Certified Public Accountants - 2007.
 26. Ziad Hashim Yahya, Ayoub Luqman (The Concept of the Internal Control System and Its Importance in Government Institutions) - 1996 - Rafidain Development Magazine - Issue (48) - University of Mosul.
 27. Nada Ismail Jabouri - (The Impact of Information Technology on Organizational Performance) - Journal of the College of Economic Sciences, Baghdad University - Issue (22) - 2009.
 28. Ziad Hashim Yahya and Ayoub Luqman - (The Concept of the Internal Control System and its Importance in Government Institutions) - Rafidain Development Journal - 1996 - Issue (48) - University of Mosul.
 29. Atallah Al-Hasban - (The Extent of Internal Auditors' Compliance in Jordanian Public Shareholding Companies) - Al-Manar Journal - Issue 1 - 2008.
 30. Fatima Abdul Jawad - (The Impact of Information Technology on the Internal Control System and Financial Matters) - Research Submitted to the First Scientific Conference Organized by the Higher Institute for Accounting and Financial Studies - 2010.